

SYNTHESIS OF DIHALOGENATED 5-AMINOACRIDINE DERIVATIVES

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Several dihalogenated-5-substituted aminoacridines and their methoxy derivatives have been described.

A large amount of work has been done to prepare suitable acridine and quinoline derivatives as antimalarial drugs (cf. Wiselogle, "Survey of Antimalarial Drugs", 1941-45, Vol. II, Part II). Magidson and Grigorovsky (*Ber.*, 1936, 69, 396) observed that 5-aminoacridine derivatives containing chlorine in any position exhibited antimalarial property. Whitmore *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1596) synthesised 2:8-dichloro-5-(δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine and reported it to have a better antimalarial property than atabrine.

With a view to ascertaining whether the dichloroacridine derivatives in general possess the antimalarial property or the particular positions occupied by two chlorine atoms confer this property, and also keeping in view the fact that the presence of the methoxy group greatly increases the lipid solubility of the drug (Shaw, *Amer. J. Hyg.*, 1928, 8, 505), synthesis of several dichloro-5-(δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridines and their 7-methoxy derivatives has been undertaken.

The general method of preparation of the above dihalogenated 5-aminoacridine derivatives consists in condensation of the requisite dichloroaniline with *o*-chloro- or *o*-bromo-benzoic acid derivatives, cyclisation of the resulting products and finally attachment of various dialkylaminoalkyl-amines. The reactions may be represented as shown below :

[R = (i) $\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{-NEt}_2$

(ii) $\text{-(CH}_2)_3\text{-N(CH}_2)_6\text{O}$

(iii) $\text{-(CH}_2)_3\text{-N(CH}_2)_6$

(iv) $\text{-(CH}_2)_3\text{-NEt}_2$ †

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† In part.

Condensation of 2:4-dichloroaniline with 6-bromo-3-methoxybenzoic acid was carried out under the conditions of Ullmann *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 2125; *Annalen*, 1907, **365**, 322; Meister, Lucein and Brunning, Ger. Pat. 145789), 2':4'-dichloro-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (I: X = CO₂H) being obtained. It was found that nitrobenzene was a more suitable solvent than *iso*amyl alcohol, as the reaction could be carried out at a higher temperature with better yields. (I: X = CO₂H) was then treated with thionyl chloride in benzene solution to obtain its acid chloride (I: X = COCl), the benzene solution of which was treated with the necessary amine to obtain the corresponding anide (I: X = CO.NHR), which was then cyclised by treating the same solution with phosphorus oxychloride without isolating (I: X = CO.NHR), when the acridine (II) was obtained as a dihydrochloride in the manner indicated in the Experimental. In some cases the dihydrochloride had very low melting point. Repeated crystallisation or precipitation did not improve the nature of the product. In such cases the product was dried at about 100° for one hour. The m.p. and analysis of such a sample are reported. In certain cases, only in working up at the final stage, the reaction mixture was extracted with alcohol and the hydrochloride of the condensed product was precipitated by the addition of either ether or acetone; while in some cases, the reaction mixture was poured into ice and liquor ammonia, and the base, thus precipitated, was collected, washed with ether and dried. It was generally purified by crystallisation from absolute alcohol. The hydrochloride was then prepared by dissolving the base in absolute alcohol or ether and passing a current of dry hydrochloric acid gas into the solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

2':4'-Dichloro-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was prepared by refluxing the mixture of 6-bromo-3-methoxybenzoic acid (7.0 g., 0.1M), anhydrous potassium carbonate (4.5 g., 0.11M), 2:4-dichloroaniline (5.1 g., 0.11M), a trace of copper powder and nitrobenzene (30 c.c.) for 5 hours at 160-70°. The reaction mixture was then steam-distilled and the residual liquid in the flask was filtered. On cooling the filtrate, the potassium salt of the acid separated out; it was collected and acidified. The green-coloured acid obtained had m.p. 230°, unchanged on further crystallisations. The filtrate after separation of the potassium salt, on acidification, also gave a small amount of the same acid, crystallised from acetic acid in pale green small needles, m.p. 230°, yield 55%. (Found: Cl, 22.94; equiv., 312. C₁₄H₁₁O₃NCl₂ requires Cl, 22.76%; equiv., 312).

2':4'-Dichloro-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxyl chloride was obtained by refluxing the above acid with a slight excess of thionyl chloride in benzene for about 20 minutes. On cooling a yellow solid separated. It was collected and crystallised from benzene in small yellow needles, m.p. 142°. It was found to be sparingly soluble in petroleum ether. (Found: Cl, 32.59. C₁₄H₁₀O₂NCl₂ requires Cl, 32.23%).

7-Methoxy-1:3-dichloro-5-(δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride was obtained by heating the mixture of the above acid chloride (1 g.), dry benzene (30 c.c.) and δ -diethylaminomethylbutylamine (0.47 g.) for half an hour. Benzene was removed by distillation; POCl₃ (3 c.c.) was then added to the reaction mixture, and refluxed for 3 hours. On removing POCl₃ by washing with petroleum ether.

TABLE I

Products.	M.P.	Cryst. from.	Form. la.	% Chlorine	
				Found.	Calc.
(1) 3':5'-Dichloro-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid	221°	Acetic acid	$C_{14}H_{11}O_2NCl_2$	22.4	22.8
(2) Acid chloride of (1)	125°	Petrol ether	$C_{14}H_{10}O_2NCl_2$	32.8	32.2
(3) 7-Methoxy-2:4-dichloro-5-(8-diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	235°	Alcohol-acetone	$C_{23}H_{31}ON_3Cl_4$	28.4 (8.0)	28.0 (8.2)
(4) 7-Methoxy-2:4-dichloro-5-(7-morpholinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	240°	Absolute alcohol	$C_{20}H_{25}O_2N_3Cl_4$	29.0	28.8
(5) 7-Methoxy-2:4-dichloro-5-(7-piperidinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	225° (decomp.)	Alcohol-ether	$C_{22}H_{27}ON_3Cl_4$	29.3	29.9
(6) 7-Methoxy-2:4-dichloro-5-(7-diethylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	237° (decomp.)	Alcohol-acetone	$C_{21}H_{27}ON_3Cl_4$	29.9	29.65
(7) 2:4-Dichloro-5-(7-morpholinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	271°	Absolute alcohol	$C_{19}H_{23}ON_3Cl_4$	31.0	30.7
(8) 2:4-Dichloro-5-(8-diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	170°	Alcohol-acetone	$C_{23}H_{29}N_3Cl_4$	30.1 (8.71)	29.9 (8.8)
(9) 2:4-Dichloro-5-(7-diethylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	255°	Absolute alcohol	$C_{20}H_{25}N_3Cl_4$	31.9	31.6
(10) 2':4'-Dichloro-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid	230°	Acetic acid	$C_{14}H_{11}O_2NCl_2$	22.9	22.8
(11) Acid chloride of (10)	142°	Benzene	$C_{14}H_{10}O_2NCl_2$	32.6	32.2
(12) 7-Methoxy-1:3-dichloro-5-(8-diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	192°	Alcohol-ether	$C_{23}H_{31}ON_3Cl_4$	28.2 (8.04)	28.0 (8.2)
(13) 7-Methoxy-1:3-dichloro-5-(7-morpholinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	285°	Alcohol	$C_{20}H_{27}ON_3Cl_4$	29.1	28.9
(14) 1:3-Dichloro-5-(7-piperidinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	220°	Abs. alcohol-ether	$C_{22}H_{27}N_3Cl_4$	31.0	30.9
(15) 1:3-Dichloro-5-(8-diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	300°	Alcohol-acetone	$C_{23}H_{29}N_3Cl_4$	29.9	29.9
(16) 2':5'-Dichloro-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid	216°	Acetic acid	$C_{14}H_{11}O_2NCl_2$	(8.69)	(8.8)
(17) Acid chloride of (16)	104°	Benzene	$C_{14}H_{10}O_2NCl_2$	32.41	32.23
(18) 7-Methoxy-1:4-dichloro-5-(7-morpholinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	236°	Alcohol	$C_{21}H_{25}O_2N_3Cl_4$	29.01	28.8
(19) 7-Methoxy-1:4-dichloro-5-(7-piperidinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	150° (decomp.)	"	$C_{22}H_{27}ON_3Cl_4$	29.11	28.92
(20) 7-Methoxy-1:4-dichloro-5-(8-diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	185°	Alcohol	$C_{23}H_{31}ON_3Cl_4$	28.26	28.0
(21) 1:4-Dichloro-5-(7-morpholinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	175°	"	$C_{20}H_{27}ON_3Cl_4$	30.96	30.7
(22) 1:4-Dichloro-5-(7-piperidinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	250°	"	$C_{21}H_{25}N_3Cl_4$	30.99	30.9
(23) 1:4-Dichloro-5-(8-diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride	325°	"	$C_{23}H_{29}N_3Cl_4$	29.90	29.9

the residue was extracted with absolute alcohol and the yellow dihydrochloride was precipitated by adding excess of dry ether. It was then purified by redissolving in fresh alcohol and reprecipitating as above dried product, m.p. 192-93° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 28.21. $C_{23}H_{31}ON_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 28.0%).

7-Methoxy-1:3-dichloro-5-(γ -morpholinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride was similarly prepared by condensing the above acid chloride with γ -morpholinopropylamine. It crystallised from alcohol in yellow granular solid, m.p. 285° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 29.01. $C_{21}H_{25}O_2N_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 28.8%).

For the sake of brevity, various substituted diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acids with their acid chlorides and various substituted 5-aminoacridine dihydrochlorides are recorded in Table I.

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